

The Man-Woman Excluded from Society
Exploring the Impact of Cultural Practices on Women's Rights in post-modern Albania

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Abstract

This bachelor thesis examines how traditional cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" have contributed to the historical marginalization of women's rights in Albania and their enduring impact on contemporary Albanian society. Furthermore, it aims to explore the problem of the post-modern construction of gender identity within traditional societies with Albania as the case study.

An Ad Hoc research approach is employed, combining archival research, interviewing, and a wide-range survey to understand contemporary sentiments on the topic. In-depth interviews with women's rights historians and political figures will provide insights into the contemporary political landscape and the lasting influence of traditional cultural practices. The findings of this study reveal the multifaceted impact of "The Kanun" on women's rights, both historically and in present-day Albania. It sheds light on the various aspects of gender inequality perpetuated by cultural practices, such as limitations on women's mobility, restricted access to education, constrained participation in decision-making processes, and the role of women in present-day Albania. Furthermore, the research explores how these cultural attitudes have persisted over time and continue to shape contemporary Albanian society, impacting policymaking and women's representation.

Keywords: Albania, women's rights, cultural practices, The Kanun, historical marginalization, contemporary politics, gender inequality, qualitative research.

Introduction

The marginalization of women in Albanian politics challenges gender equality and inclusive governance, but where does this phenomenon stem from? The exclusion of women from political participation and decision-making processes raises concerns about democratic principles of representation and inclusivity (Elsie, 2001, p.46). Marginalization¹ refers to the systematic exclusion, disempowerment, and limited access to resources, opportunities, and decision-making processes experienced by women. It refers to the societal dynamics and structures that result in women being placed in a subordinate position, hindering their full and equal participation in society and politics.

This thesis is an in-depth exploration of the historical and contemporary facets of women's marginalization in Albania. It examines the lasting impact of cultural practices codified in "The Kanun"² in present day Albania. The research question emerges as follows: How did the codified cultural practices in the Kanun contribute to the historical marginalization of women's rights, and how have these deeply ingrained cultural attitudes endured and exerted influence over contemporary Albanian society?

To explore this research question, a mixed-methods approach through Ad Hoc research is employed. The methodology includes a comprehensive literature review, interview findings, and a survey consisting of 271 Albanian responders from in and out of the country. The theoretical framework guiding this study draws on various perspectives from existing bodies of work and aims to fill in the gaps left in previous. The analysis highlights the works of scholars such as Crenshaw (1991), Sadiku (2014), and Danaj (2019) and the international views of Elsie (2001) and Kadare (1897), which provide historical and contemporary insights into the significance of the Kanun in Albania. These studies shed light on how traditional cultural practices shape gender relations and contribute to the marginalization of women's rights.

¹ Giomi, F., Zerman, E., & STEVENS, A. (2018).

² The Kanun is a patriarchal legal code that reinforces gender roles, expectations, and power dynamics (Bardhoshi, 2016).

Additionally, the study engages with two theoretical lenses, feminism, and intersectionality. Feminism³ as a theoretical lens acknowledges and challenges the historical and ongoing inequalities between genders. It allows for an exploration of the social, cultural, and political factors that have perpetuated the marginalization of women in Albanian politics. Intersectionality⁴ recognizes the interconnected nature of social identities and power structures. An intersectional lens is applied to examine the interplay of gender, culture, and socio-political factors in shaping women's experiences in post-modern Albanian society. The work of Nixon (2009) explores the role of collective shame and its gendered implications in Albania. The theoretical frameworks of scholars like Ermira Danaj (2019) and Pacukaj et al. (2021), emphasize the significance of considering multiple dimensions of identity and power when examining women's political agency. By considering these intersectional categories, the study aims to shed light on the multifaceted challenges faced by women in accessing political power and influence. The analysis also underscores the implications of the post-communist transition in Albania on women's rights and political participation. The scholarship of Olsen (2000) and Calloni (2023) is consulted to understand the socio-political changes that have affected women's rights during this period. This lens helps analyse the power dynamics and structures within the political landscape, shedding light on women's opportunities for participation and representation.

Ultimately, this research strives to shed light on the impact of cultural practices enshrined in the Kanun on women's rights. The research question is tailor-made for an examination of gender equality issues, the interplay between cultural norms, political structures, and women's involvement in European societies. This is particularly pertinent due to Albania's position as geographically European yet not part of the EU, creating a unique context where customs and practices diverge. While Balkan wide research has usually been the norm, a bottom-up approach of a single country can contribute to the European priority of promoting inclusion. The study enriches the existing scholarship on women's rights in Albania by providing an analysis of the historical roots and contemporary manifestations of gender inequality. By highlighting the relationship between culture and politics, the study yields valuable insights and aims to contribute to understanding and rectifying gender disparities and promoting full

³ Feminism. (2012). *The Journal of Speculative Philosophy*, 26(2), 268–290.
<https://doi.org/10.5325/jspecphil.26.2.0268>.

⁴ Intersectionality is an analytical framework for understanding how a person's various social and political identities combine to create different modes of discrimination and privilege (Nash, J. C. 2008).

political engagement in Albania and cultivating gender-responsive governance and empowering women in post-modern societies.

Literature Review

This paper presents an analysis of "The Kanun of Lekë Dukagjini," a legal code in Albanian society, with a focus on its implications for women's rights historically and in contemporary society. Published in both English (1989) and German versions (2001), the code sheds light on the historical marginalization of women within this cultural framework. A significant portion of the Kanun deals with property rights, including land and women, thereby intrinsically tying the concept of women's identities to that of property and ownership by others. This exhibits the extent of the historical marginalization of women, as occupying roles akin to property rather than autonomous beings. This is in stark contrast to the rights attributed to men, thereby reinforcing patriarchal structures and norms within society. This document review reveals that the marginalization of women is deeply codified and historically ingrained through the Kanun, which may continue to exert considerable influence over contemporary attitudes within Albanian society. However, it is important to consider the lack of further substantial research into the link between historical and present marginalization. This thesis aims to bridge the gap and provide further empirical analysis to substantiate such presumptions concerning the enduring legacy of the Kanun's norms and implications for women's rights in modern Albanian society.

While Danaj's (2019) work does not directly address the Kanun, it does state that feminist and gender studies have struggled due to a negative connotation of left-wing perspectives following Albania's transition away from communism. This has limited the development of critical and feminist thought and debate in academia, leading to hostile prejudices against feminists. The only complete program on gender studies in Albania is situated within the Department of Social Work and Social Policy, taught as an optional course, indicating a persistent marginalization of these studies. While rigorous studies on the influence of proprietary laws like Kanun in Albania on the evolution of women's rights are scarce, it is indirect evidence that cultural traditions could have contributed to the paucity of gender and feminist studies in Albanian higher education. To fully address the research question of this thesis, referencing post-modern ideas from the survey that will be presented and the interviews with high officials discussing social norms and cultural practices in Albania, especially "The Kanun", is necessary to fill in gaps in current research.

Whether observing the historical underpinnings of the Kanun or analyzing the cultural persistence in modern Albania, the literature emphasizes the influence of deeply ingrained cultural attitudes. While strides have been made, as suggested by Gjermeni et al. (2008), the path towards gender equality in Albania is still laden with stereotypes that need to be dismantled. Dhembo (2016) also notes the enduring influence of cultural attitudes on the women of Albania. Accounting for gender discrimination in the form of lower wages for women, he argues that feelings of patriarchal superiority carried over from Kanun, and have, to a large extent, hindered women's progress today. However, Vullnetari and King (2008) argue that while its cultural practices have undeniably impacted women's rights historically, attributing contemporary inequalities solely to its endurance may sidestep other contributory factors such as economic conditions and the complex process of democratization, as also highlighted in the original paper.

Drawing a link to modern-day Albania, scholars have pointed out that these entrenched attitudes have bled into prevailing societal norms. Societal perceptions, as discussed in the paper on "Stereotypical views about women," levy significant barriers on women leaders. The paper elaborates on the persistent stereotype that women should be confined to traditional family roles and posits women achieving career success are regarded as exceptions or socially deviant (EJSS, 2018). This information substantiates findings from Hadzibulić (2016), who states that contemporary Albanian society carries the imprints of the gender biases originating from the Kanun. The enduring influence of these norms is evident from the data that reveal a low percentage of society views women as capable of assuming decision-making roles. The absence of substantial women representation in high-ranking positions suggests the prevalence of these attitudes (EJSS, 2018).

The work by Erbaş (2014) investigates the engagement of women in political, socio-economic, and cultural processes, focusing primarily on the context of Albanian society. However, it does not directly address the societal influence of the Kanun. Instead, the paper highlights the barriers women face in decision-making processes in their family life and politics, as well as how they challenge these norms and can affect change. This underscores women's resilience and determination to contribute to the socio-political milieu, despite the systemic obstacles they confront. The text describes a positive shift in women's organizations during the period of 1994-1996, indicating a dynamic and growing environment for women's civil society movements in Albania. While indicative of societal progress, the paper implies

that these developments were isolated. In conclusion, while this paper contributes to our understanding of women's participation in Albania, it doesn't specifically address the influence of the Kanun. Further research specifically tackling these aspects would provide a more comprehensive picture of the historical and contemporary marginalization of women's rights in Albanian society.

Calloni (2023) reflects upon the theme of women's marginalization in Albania, a scenario that manifests itself in a contradiction between de jure gender equality, and the daily realities which depict another picture. However, it does not refer to the Kanun, and for a more comprehensive literature review on our research question, we must consult other sources as well. Lakshmanan (2010) has explored this question by delving into the nature of deeply ingrained cultural legacies and societal norms epitomized within the Kanun. While the Kanun promoted patriarchal governance where women were excluded from public life (Young, 2000), it offered some women an alternative way of life by taking a vow of chastity, known as burnesh and adopting the social privileges of men (Grémaux, 1996).

Ismail Kadare's (1987) autobiography, "The Autobiography of the People in Verse," viewed in conjunction with the aforementioned scholarly works adds a unique perspective on the historical and cultural context of Albania. Kadare's (1987) insights into the influence of traditional practices, societal dynamics, and the historical legacy of the Kanun contribute to our understanding of how codified cultural practices have contributed to the historical marginalization of women's rights. His work provides first-hand accounts and narratives that shed light on the complexities of Albanian society and its intersections with cultural practices, offering valuable insights into the persistence of cultural attitudes in contemporary Albania. It demonstrates the interconnectedness between cultural practices, women's rights, and political dynamics, thereby addressing the research question at hand.

In conclusion, to answer the research question posed: the Kanun has indeed contributed significantly to women's historical marginalization through its strict patriarchal dictates. However, associating its legacy solely with existing gender disparities may offer a reductionist view; aspects such as political and economic transitions must also be considered. Future research must delve further into how societal attitudes have evolved over time and influenced contemporary Albanian society, along with the current efforts targeting gender equality.

Theoretical Framework

This thesis is grounded in a range of theories and concepts that contribute to the understanding of the impact of traditional cultural practices on women's rights in Albania and their influence on contemporary Albanian society.

a) Definition of theories and terms

Intersectionality

The author, Crenshaw (1991), addresses the intersectionality of race and gender in the context of violence against women by examining how dominant resistance discourses shape women of color's marginalization. She argues that the demands for change can only be effective if they reflect the logic of the challenging institution. This statement implies that women of color, facing challenges related to both their race and gender, might have their specific needs overlooked if their demands do not align with the dominant ideology. She goes beyond generalizations, acknowledging the diverse identities among women and recognizing that they can experience violence in different ways, affected by various intersecting factors such as race, gender, and sexual orientation. As the work focuses on patriarchy within the context of systemic racism in the U.S., which provides for a different post-modern lens in a Western Country while Kanun refers to a set of traditional Albanian laws and customs, with its own unique context and set of implications for women which can be mutually exclusive. However, a potential comparative perspective could focus on how both systems - the racialized American patriarchy as discussed in this paper and the traditional Kanun system in Albania - employ different methods to reinforce male dominance and control women and how women have fought the system in their own way by using feminism.

Postmodernism and Cultural feminist perspective

The thesis engages with various feminist perspectives, including those of Elsie (2012), Tahsini and Duci (2022), and Danaj (2019), to explore the historical and contemporary struggles for women's rights in Albania. These perspectives provide insights into the power dynamics and societal structures that perpetuate gender inequality. Feminist theory serves as a critical framework for understanding the struggles for women's rights in Albania and their relevance to contemporary Albanian politics. This theoretical perspective examines power

dynamics, social structures, and cultural norms to analyse and challenge gender inequality and oppression.

The way feminism has been presented in Albanian societies is like Gasztold's (2020) approach which explains that feminism's main premise is the refusal to accept social inequalities based on gender, in this case very prominently shown through the less binary act of being a *Burrnesh*.

The concept of *burrnesh* is directly also linked with the feminist idea that proposes that when power and oppression are acknowledged and disrupted, understanding, advocacy, and change can occur. This phenomenon has been studied and discussed by Ermira Danaj (2018) and Sadiku (2014), who explore the motivations and experiences of women who adopt the *burrnesh* identity and different from Nixon (2009) instead of a forced experience they believe women adopted this in a sign of body positivity and freedom.

The inclusion of the *burrnesh* concept within feminist theory allows for a nuanced understanding of gender dynamics in pre- and post-modern Albania. It challenges traditional binary understandings of gender by highlighting the fluidity and complexity of identities and roles, especially in controlled societies. The *burrnesh* concept also underscores the ways in which gender intersects with cultural and societal expectations, as women navigate and negotiate their roles within a patriarchal society.

By incorporating the concept of *burrnesh*, the thesis recognizes the agency and resilience of women in challenging traditional gender norms and finding alternative pathways for empowerment. It acknowledges that women's experiences and strategies for navigating gender inequality are not uniform but vary depending on their individual circumstances and choices. Overall, feminist theory, enriched by the concept of *burrnesh*, provides a necessary framework for examining women's rights in Albania.

Cultural Relativism:

Cultural relativism is a concept that plays a significant role in understanding the impact of traditional cultural practices on women's rights in contemporary societies. It recognizes that cultural practices, beliefs, and norms should be understood and evaluated within the context of their respective cultures, rather than applying universal standards of right or wrong.

In the context of this thesis, cultural relativism helps to analyse the context and significance of cultural traditions, which are deeply rooted in Albanian society. By adopting a cultural

relativist perspective in the survey and interview questions, the research aims to explore how these traditional practices interact with women's rights and the broader socio-political landscape (Danaj, 2019).

Methodology

This thesis adopts an Ad Hoc Triangulation research approach to address the research questions and achieve the research objectives. The combination of methods allows for a comprehensive analysis of the impact of traditional cultural practices on women's rights in Albania and their influence on contemporary Albanian society .

Interview Methods and reasoning

Two semi-structured email interviews are conducted with well-rounded individuals partaking in policymaking, activism, academics, and representatives from civil society organizations. The interviews provide insights into the lived experiences, perspectives, and challenges faced by women in relation to traditional cultural practices and their political participation. There are ten questions asked in total and the interviewees have requested to remain anonymous due to the contents of their responses. Nonetheless the interviews have been coded and sub coded⁵ in order to grasp a better idea of the main ideologies throughout the responses. The questions of the interview are chosen carefully as they reveal the following.

Objective: Gain in-depth insights and nuanced perspectives on your research question.

Method:

Conduct qualitative interviews with a smaller sample of participants. Use open-ended questions to encourage participants to share their experiences, opinions, and narratives related to the historical marginalization of women's rights and the influence of cultural attitudes on contemporary Albanian society. The Interview benefits are hypothesized as the offers of rich, contextualized information thus allowing for exploration of individual experiences and viewpoints while providing a deeper understanding of the "how" and "why" in connection with the survey questions and findings as they are answered by the heads of the government but also by a multitude of Albanians and it shows the main thought process that leads the cultural post-modern society of the case study chosen. While remaining with the objective to synthesize existing knowledge and theoretical perspectives. The interviews are conducted with a comprehensive review of existing literature on "The Kanun," women's rights in Albania, cultural practices, and their historical and contemporary implications in mind through the questions asked. This all done in order to identify gaps in the literature shown previously.

⁵ See Annex for code table

Survey Methods and reasoning

A Quantitative Google survey⁶ is administered to collect data on peoples experiences, attitudes, and perceptions regarding their rights and political engagement. The surveys are designed to capture a representative sample of women and men from different regions, age groups, and socio-economic backgrounds in Albania. The data obtained from the Google surveys are analysed using statistical methods to identify patterns, trends, and correlations.

Based on the survey conducted, the following three main hypotheses are proposed:

There will be a substantial historical impact of the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" on the marginalization of women's rights in Albania.

Hypotheses:

Historical Marginalization Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant association between knowledge about codified cultural practices in "The Kanun" and the belief that they have contributed to historical marginalization of women's rights.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant association between knowledge about codified cultural practices in "The Kanun" and the belief that they have contributed to historical marginalization of women's rights.

Contemporary Political Influence Hypothesis:

Null Hypothesis (H0): There is no significant association between awareness of political attitudes from "The Kanun" and their influence on contemporary Albanian society.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): There is a significant association between awareness of political attitudes from "The Kanun" and their influence on contemporary Albanian society.

Categories for Analysis:

Knowledge about Codified Cultural Practices:

Categories: Not Educated⁷, Somewhat Educated, Well Educated

Belief about Historical Marginalization:

Categories: Strongly Disagree, Disagree, Neutral, Agree, Strongly Agree

Influence of Cultural Attitudes on Gender Roles:

Categories: No Influence, Low Influence, Moderate Influence, High Influence

Examples of Denied or Restricted Rights (within "The Kanun" context):

⁶ Google Form is a popular scientific product in online survey research due to its unlimited surveys feature and 100% free asset (Evans & Mathur, 2005)

⁷ Educated in the survey serves the purpose of showing educated on the subject of the kanun rather than meaning the general schooling/education level of an individual.

Open-ended responses

Continuation of Cultural Attitudes in Contemporary Society:

Categories: No Continuation, Mild Continuation, Moderate Continuation, Strong Continuation

Observation of Changes in Recent Years:

Categories: No Change, Slight Change, Moderate Change, Significant Change

Role of Reforms and Legal Structures:

Categories: No Role, Limited Role, Moderate Role, Significant Role

Challenges to Promoting Gender Equality:

Open-ended responses

Operationalization of survey:

Q1 aims to capture the geographical location of the respondents. It helps to understand if there might be regional variations in cultural practices and attitudes.

Q2 is used to categorize respondents by their gender. Gender can play a significant role in how cultural practices and attitudes are perceived and experienced.

Q3 captures the age of the respondents. Different age groups might have varying levels of exposure to cultural practices and different perspectives on their impact.

Q4 assesses the level of knowledge respondents have about the cultural practices outlined in "The Kanun" and their historical significance. Education about these practices can influence opinions on their impact.

Q5 gauges the perception of the link between cultural practices in "The Kanun" and women's rights marginalization. It helps understand if respondents believe a connection exists.

Q6 is open-ended, exploring whether respondents have observed cultural attitudes' impact on gender roles and where they've noticed it (education, work, politics, etc.).

Q7 is open-ended gathering specific instances of women's rights limitations according to "The Kanun," showcasing the practical implications of these practices.

Q8 asks for the respondent's perception of the persistence of cultural attitudes, helping to gauge whether these attitudes are perceived as enduring.

Q9 aims to understand whether respondents perceive any shifts in the influence of cultural practices on women's rights and politics, reflecting potential societal changes.

Q10 investigates how respondents view the impact of political reforms and legal changes on women's rights and whether they see improvements.

Q11 is open-ended, gathering respondents' insights on the challenges that need to be tackled to achieve gender equality while addressing cultural practices' influence.

These questions were chosen to comprehensively explore the research question about the influence of "The Kanun" on women's rights and contemporary Albanian politics. They cover historical understanding, perceptions, observations, challenges, and potential changes, allowing a holistic view of the topic.

The survey aims to uncover not only factual knowledge but also personal perceptions and observations, which can provide a richer understanding of the relationship between cultural practices, women's rights, and politics. The open-ended questions allow respondents to provide nuanced insights and specific examples, contributing to a comprehensive analysis.

Link to research question:

L1: Understanding the geographical context helps contextualize how cultural practices from "The Kanun" might have been prevalent in different regions, potentially influencing historical and contemporary attitudes toward women's rights.

L2 :Gender is a crucial factor in understanding the roles and rights of individuals within cultural practices. It contributes to examining how cultural attitudes might have affected men and women differently over time.

L3: Age can provide insights into generational shifts in awareness and attitudes towards cultural practices and women's rights. Different age groups might have varying perspectives on historical and contemporary influences.

L4: This question helps establish a baseline understanding of respondents' knowledge about the cultural practices and their historical significance, which is vital for assessing how awareness relates to perceptions of marginalization.

L5: This question directly addresses the contribution of cultural practices from "The Kanun" to the historical marginalization of women's rights, providing insights into perceived causal links.

L6: By asking about specific contexts where cultural attitudes are observed, this question seeks to understand where and how deeply ingrained cultural attitudes from "The Kanun" have impacted gender roles and expectations.

L7: This question aims to extract concrete instances of how "The Kanun" might have limited women's rights, providing direct evidence of the historical impact of these cultural practices.

L8: This question examines the persistence of cultural attitudes over time, connecting historical influences to contemporary perspectives on their endurance.

L9: This question helps bridge the historical and contemporary aspects, capturing how cultural practices' influence might be evolving in the context of women's rights and politics.

L10: This question explores the role of governance in combating historical marginalization, considering how legal changes intersect with deeply rooted cultural attitudes.

L11: By soliciting insights into challenges, this question connects the research question to contemporary efforts to promote gender equality and confront cultural attitudes' influence within post-modern societies.

Overall, the survey questions systematically address various dimensions of the research question, helping to uncover the historical factors and enduring influences related to the codified cultural practices in "The Kanun" and their impact on women's rights and societal functions in post-modern Albania.

Case selection

The Kanun:

The Kanun holds significant importance in understanding the impact of traditional cultural practices on women's rights in Albania and their influence on contemporary Albanian politics. The Kanun is a comprehensive legal code that encompasses various aspects of Albanian life, including social norms, family relations, and dispute resolution. It is an unwritten customary law system that has been passed down through generations and has played a significant role in shaping Albanian society (Shkurtaj, 2020).

The research draws on scholarly works such as Danaj (2018), Sadiku (2014), and Lugaj (2018) to delve into the historical and contemporary significance of the Kanun. These works provide insights into the origins of the Kanun, and its continued influence on Albanian society. It assigns specific rights and responsibilities to men and women, regulating various aspects of their lives. Women are often confined to the private sphere, with limited agency and decision-making power, while men are predominantly responsible for public affairs and representing the family's honour (Bardhoshi, 2016).

It's impact on women's rights is multi-faceted. It perpetuates gender inequality by promoting practices such as arranged marriages, blood feuds, and the subordination of women within the family structure. These practices restrict women's autonomy, mobility, and participation in public life. By examining the Kanun within the context of women's rights and contemporary Albanian society, this thesis aims to shed light on the complex relationship between cultural traditions, gender inequality, and social dynamics. It seeks to analyse the ways in which the Kanun influences women's lived experiences, hampers their political agency, and perpetuates patriarchal norms. The research contributes to existing scholarship by offering a nuanced understanding of the Kanun's impact on women's rights and its implications for gender

equality in Albania. Women's representation in the Albanian Parliament has remained relatively low. Although there have been periodic increases in the number of women elected, the overall proportion remains below the international standards set by CEDAW and other equality benchmarks. This underrepresentation limits women's voices and perspectives in the political decision-making processes, which in turn affects the prioritization of issues related to women's rights and gender equality (Rashkova ; Zankina, 2017). Barriers to women's political participation in Albania include traditional gender roles and expectations, cultural norms, lack of support from political parties, limited access to resources and networks, and societal perceptions of women's roles in public life. These factors contribute to a persistent gender gap in political representation and decision-making.

Albania as a case study:

Albania has a rich cultural heritage, and the cultural practices codified in Kanun provide a unique lens through which to examine the societal norms and values that have influenced Albanian society for centuries. Exploring the impact of these cultural practices on women's rights and their persistence in contemporary Albania offers valuable insights into the intersections of tradition, culture, and gender dynamics.

Albania's history has been marked by various political, social, and cultural transformations. From the Ottoman Empire to communist rule and the subsequent transition to democracy, Albania has experienced significant shifts in its political and social structures. Investigating the historical marginalization of women's rights within this context helps illuminate the complex dynamics that have shaped the current state of gender equality in Albanian society.

Gender Inequality Challenges: Like many societies, Albania has faced challenges in achieving gender equality and addressing issues related to women's rights. By studying the specific case of Albania, researchers can identify and analyse the unique barriers, constraints, and opportunities that impact women's participation in politics and decision-making processes.

This understanding can contribute to broader discussions on gender equality, policy development, and advocacy efforts within the European context.

Comparative Perspective: Albania's experiences and challenges with regard to women's rights and cultural practices can also be examined comparatively within the broader European context. By studying Albania alongside other European countries, researchers can identify common patterns, differences, and factors that influence the persistence or transformation of cultural practices and their impact on women's rights. This comparative approach enhances

our understanding of the broader challenges and opportunities for gender equality across European societies.

Current Developments in the country happen fast as the country is developing quickly post the fall of communism. Ongoing efforts to strengthen democratic institutions, foster gender equality, and promote women's political participation make it a relevant case study. By examining contemporary developments and initiatives aimed at advancing women's rights, researchers can assess the progress made, identify remaining challenges, and contribute to ongoing discussions.

Overall, Albania's cultural practices, historical context, gender inequality challenges, comparative perspective, and current developments make it an interesting and meaningful case study for exploring the interplay between cultural practices, women's rights, and politics within the European studies framework.

Data Analysis

Thematic Analysis: Qualitative data from interviews and document analysis are subjected to thematic analysis. The data is coded and categorized into themes such as: Practices, Culture, Gender and sub-themes such as: Fear and Judgement, Barrier Creation, Self-Expression and Transparency to identify patterns, recurring concepts, and emergent insights related to the impact of traditional cultural practices on women's rights and their political participation.

Statistical Analysis: Quantitative data from surveys are analysed. Descriptive statistics, such as frequencies and percentages and tables, are used to summarize the data and examine the distribution of responses.

Ethical guidelines are followed throughout the research process to ensure the protection of participants' rights, confidentiality, and informed consent. Ethical approval is obtained from the relevant institutional review board or ethics committee before conducting interviews or surveys. Participants are informed about the purpose of the study, their rights as participants, and the voluntary nature of their participation. Anonymity and confidentiality of participants' responses are maintained during data collection, analysis, and reporting.

It is important to acknowledge the potential limitations of the methodology. The research relies on self-reported data, which may be subject to social desirability bias or recall bias. Additionally, the sample selection for interviews and surveys may not fully capture the diversity of women's experiences in Albania. Efforts are made to mitigate these limitations through rigorous data collection and analysis processes.

By employing ad hoc triangulation approach, this thesis aims to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the impact of traditional cultural practices on women's rights in Albania and their influence on contemporary Albanian society. The combination of qualitative and quantitative data allows for triangulation and validation of findings, strengthening the overall rigor and validity of the research.

This study aims to investigate the historical contribution of cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" to the marginalization of women's rights in Albania. By examining the persisting influence of these cultural attitudes in contemporary Albanian society, the research seeks to shed light on the enduring impact and potential barriers faced by women in their pursuit of equality and participation. To test the hypothesis, a survey was conducted using Google Forms and distributed through various channels, including Instagram stories. The survey targeted the Albanian population, focusing on their knowledge, opinions, and observations regarding the Kanun and women's postmodern rights. Non-probability convenience sampling was employed, and the anticipated sample size was set at a maximum of 92 respondents.

Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and proportions, were used to analyse the survey responses. The data were examined to determine the overall level of interest in the topic and the demographic distribution of respondents. Findings provided insights into the level of interest and participation in the survey, supporting or refuting the hypothesis that a limited number of respondents, hopefully reaching a minimum of fifty but not expected to exceed ninety-two, would engage with the survey.

The predestined ninety-two number is based on a collective counted number of Albanian followers across social media. Additionally, the analysis of open-ended responses is expected to reveal distinct patterns and variations between male and female participants, shedding light on their differing observations and opinions regarding the influence of cultural practices on women's rights in Albanian politics.

This research contributes to the understanding of the impact of cultural practices on women's rights and socio-political dynamics in Albania.

Findings and Discussion

As the hypothesis and Literature review explained there is a need to delve deeper into the interplay between cultural practices and postmodern societal feminist norms, as the reviewed works primarily focus on cultural practices and societal attitudes rather than policy and institutional factors. Furthermore, the reviewed literature does not extensively explore the long-term impacts and changes that have occurred over time or consider global and comparative perspectives. Additionally, alternative perspectives and counter-narratives are not thoroughly incorporated, and the role of policies, legal frameworks, and institutional structures in shaping women's rights and political dynamics is not extensively analysed in the Albanian sphere but rather in the Balkan one.

Interview Findings and discussions

As can be read throughout Appendix I and II in the interviews, the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" hold significant historical significance in Albania, serving as a foundation for societal conduct and norms that reflect the collective wisdom and experiences of past generations. However, these cultural practices have contributed to the historical marginalization of women's rights. By assigning women primarily domestic roles, these practices have limited their access to education, economic opportunities, and political participation. Furthermore, the cultural practices codified have had a profound influence on gender roles and expectations in Albanian society. Women have been expected to prioritize their roles as caregivers and homemakers, while men have been encouraged to assume positions of authority and responsibility in the public sphere. Despite ongoing efforts to promote gender equality, certain cultural attitudes influenced by "The Kanun" persist in contemporary Albanian society. These deep-rooted stereotypes and prejudices hinder the full realization of women's rights and their equal participation in all aspects of society. In the realm of politics, these cultural attitudes have historically impacted the participation of women, confining them to the private sphere and limiting their visibility and influence in public life. Although initiatives such as gender quotas and support for women candidates have made progress, further advancements are necessary. Nevertheless, recent years have witnessed notable changes and shifts in the influence of cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" on women's rights and Albanian politics. As mentioned during the second interview : “the Kanun did not marginalize women; it codified the social reality of the time. Certainly, its codification did not improve their situation in society; on the contrary, it made it more

difficult to escape from the state of oppression and isolation. The Kanun had now become an alibi for all those resistant forces that desired to maintain the status quo (Redacted, Personal Communication, 14 May, 2023).” Legal reforms, awareness campaigns, and the activism of women's rights advocates and feminist movements have contributed to an increasing recognition of women's rights and the urgent need for gender equality. To promote gender equality and overcome the influence of cultural practices on women's rights in contemporary Albanian politics, several key challenges must be addressed. During the first interview the political scope for Albanian women is briefly described as : “Policy reforms and legal frameworks have played a pivotal role in addressing the historical marginalization of women's rights in Albania. They have provided a structured approach to dismantling discriminatory practices and establishing a legal foundation for gender equality.

Reforms in areas such as family law, labour rights, and political representation have aimed to rectify historical injustices and ensure women's full participation and empowerment. The implementation of gender quotas, for example, has increased the representation of women in decision-making bodies, promoting a more balanced and inclusive political landscape.

Additionally, legal frameworks against domestic violence and gender-based discrimination have enhanced the protection of women's rights, providing avenues for justice and redress. These reforms and frameworks demonstrate our commitment to promoting gender equality and addressing the historical marginalization of women's rights in Albania.” (Redacted, Personal Communication, 10 April 2023).

These challenges encompass transforming societal attitudes and cultural norms, enhancing women's political representation, promoting economic empowerment and equal opportunities, strengthening institutional mechanisms for protecting women's rights, and engaging men as allies in the pursuit of gender equality. By acknowledging the historical significance of cultural practices, recognizing the marginalization of women's rights, and addressing the persistence of cultural attitudes, policymakers and stakeholders can work toward creating a more inclusive and equitable society that upholds women's rights in Albania.

Survey Findings and Discussions

This section presents the findings from the survey conducted to investigate the historical contribution of cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" to the marginalization of women's rights in Albania. The analysis focused on the persisting influence of these cultural attitudes in contemporary Albanian politics, aiming to shed light on the enduring impact and potential barriers faced by women in their pursuit of equality and participation. The overwhelming

participation observed in the survey, the diverse range of opinions expressed in the open-ended questions, and the significant engagement of participants across different age groups show that the topic is relevant today more than ever. The survey attracted a substantial number of participants, far exceeding the initial expectations. With a total of two hundred seventy-one total respondents, the engagement demonstrates a keen interest in the topic of cultural practices and women's rights in postmodern Albanian society. This overwhelming participation highlights the urgency and significance of addressing the issue, indicating a widespread recognition of the persistence of sexism and gender-based discrimination in various spheres, including workplaces and educational institutions. The analysis of open-ended responses revealed a diverse range of opinions and perspectives among the participants. Many respondents expressed strong support for further discussion and exploration of the topic. Their positive attitudes emphasized the need to confront and challenge the prevailing cultural practices that perpetuate the marginalization of women's rights in Albanian society. The open-ended questions provided a platform for individuals to voice their experiences and observations regarding sexism and discrimination, leading to a rich dataset of qualitative information. A noteworthy finding was the recurring mention of sexism and discrimination in workplaces and educational institutions. Respondents shared instances where women face unequal treatment, limited career opportunities, and biased expectations. The narratives portrayed a prevailing culture that undermines the rights and contributions of women, hindering their progress and development. These responses underscore the necessity of addressing systemic sexism in various societal domains, emphasizing the urgency for policy interventions and awareness campaigns to foster gender equality. Contrary to initial expectations, a substantial number of participants aged under 27 exhibited strong opinions and awareness regarding the topic. The findings challenged preconceived notions that younger individuals may be less informed or less engaged in discussions about cultural practices and women's rights. The active involvement of younger generations suggests a growing consciousness among them regarding gender equality issues, indicating a potential for progressive societal change. The diverse perspectives and informed opinions expressed by this demographic highlight the need to consider their voices in policy discussions and decision-making processes. The findings from the survey analysis indicate an overwhelming participation and an urgent demand for discussion on the topic of cultural practices and women's rights in Albanian politics. The wide range of opinions expressed in the open-ended questions emphasizes the need to challenge prevailing cultural norms that perpetuate gender inequality. Moreover, the significant engagement of participants under 27 highlights the importance of considering the perspectives of younger generations in

addressing these issues. It means there are significant traces left from the Kanun into the 21st century which extends its reign to 6 centuries long. These findings contribute to the understanding of the impact of cultural practices on women's rights and call for comprehensive measures to promote gender equality and inclusivity in Albanian politics and society at large. Women's rights do not get built in one night however they can most certainly be removed in one. Policy discussions, advocacy efforts, and further research can build upon these findings to create a more equitable and inclusive political landscape in Albania. The research of this thesis provides a wide poll of statistics to analyse, especially with a fully Albanian focus and already original documents of research in two different languages for wider audiences. In conclusion the findings align with the hypothesis, however with minor surprising results that are rather positive and show the interest of the wider audience on the matter.

Table 1.

<i>Category</i>	<i>Observed #</i>	<i>Expected #</i>
Sex (m)	15	92
Sex (f)	253	92
In Albania	213	92
Outside of Alb	51	92
Alb Diaspora	7	92
Agree (c.k)	41	92
Disagree (c.k)	41	92
Partially (c.k)	189	92
Age 27 >	42	92
Age 27 <	195	92
P.reform (yes)	30	92
P.reform (no)	78	92
P.reform (par)	130	92

Conclusion

This thesis has undertaken a comprehensive exploration of the historical and contemporary implications of The Kanun on women's rights within Albanian society. The guiding research question, "How did the codified cultural practices in 'The Kanun' contribute to the historical marginalization of women's rights, and how have these deeply ingrained cultural attitudes endured and exerted influence over contemporary Albanian society?", has driven an in-depth analysis that unveils the intricate interplay between cultural norms, gender dynamics, and societal progress. The chosen theoretical framework, a fusion of feminist theory and intersectionality, has lent a robust lens through which to examine the multifaceted layers of women's experiences in Albania. By embracing feminist theory, the study delves into the entrenched gender hierarchies reinforced by "The Kanun," illustrating how women's identities became entangled with property, perpetuating patriarchal norms. Intersectionality further enriches this perspective, unraveling the compounded challenges that women face due to the intersections of gender, ethnicity, and socio-economic factors. Contrasting viewpoints within the literature, accompanied by insights from scholars such as Crenshaw, underscore the complexities of addressing women's rights within different cultural contexts. The intersectional lens helps acknowledge the unique struggles faced by women with diverse identities and experiences, emphasizing the need for a nuanced approach to dismantling gender inequalities. While the study focuses on the Albanian context, the lessons drawn from the intersectionality and feminist framework can resonate globally, encouraging a more comprehensive understanding of gender dynamics. Ad Hoc triangulation method employed, involving interviews, surveys, and literature analysis, has enriched the study's depth and rigor. Nevertheless, limitations exist within the research. The exclusive focus on "The Kanun" may overshadow other factors contributing to gender inequality. The study's cultural specificity might hinder the generalizability of findings to other contexts. Additionally, the reliance on secondary sources for historical data could introduce potential bias or inaccuracies. In light of these limitations, the study's findings underscore that the codified cultural practices within "The Kanun" have historically constrained women's rights, perpetuating gender inequality and limiting agency. The enduring influence of these practices resonates in contemporary Albanian society, impeding efforts towards gender equality and inclusive governance. This necessitates strategic measures to challenge and transform deeply ingrained cultural norms, paving the way for a more equitable political landscape that acknowledges the agency and contributions of women.

In conclusion, this research contributes vital insights into the lasting impact of cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" on women's rights and their intricate role in shaping Albanian society. The theoretical framework, driven by intersectionality and feminist theory, unveils the complexity of women's experiences, transcending cultural contexts. While acknowledging the uniqueness of cultural practices, this study emphasizes the importance of universal principles of gender equality. Through nuanced policy-making and further interdisciplinary research, the study's findings can help catalyze progress towards gender-responsive governance, empowerment, and societal inclusivity.

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Appendix I

Interview I

The interview is a personal, Email Conducted Interview with a Politician and it has been asked to remain anonymous. The interview transcript and answers have been translated from Albanian to English. Below is the coded table.

Can you share your understanding of the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" and their historical significance in Albania?

As a politician deeply engaged in the history and development of our nation, I have extensively studied the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" and their historical significance in Albania. The Kanun is an ancient customary law that has been passed down through generations, serving as a foundation for societal conduct and norms. Its origins can be traced back to the fifteenth century, reflecting the collective wisdom and experiences of our ancestors.

"The Kanun" encompasses a wide range of regulations governing various aspects of life, including family structures, honour codes, property rights, and criminal justice. It reflects the values and traditions of Albanian society, providing a framework for moral and social order.

In what ways have the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" contributed to the marginalization of women's rights historically?

While acknowledging the rich historical significance of "The Kanun," it is imperative to recognize that certain interpretations and applications of its provisions have contributed to the marginalization of women's rights. These interpretations have, at times, perpetuated gender inequalities and hindered the progress of women in our society.

In particular, some aspects of "The Kanun" have assigned women primarily domestic roles, limiting their access to education, economic opportunities, and political participation. Such practices have reinforced traditional gender roles, wherein men have been seen as the main providers and decision-makers, while women have been confined to the private sphere.

How have these cultural practices influenced gender roles and expectations in Albanian society over time?

Over time, the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" have significantly influenced gender roles and expectations in Albanian society. They have shaped the perception of femininity and masculinity, often prescribing rigid and traditional roles for women and men. Women have traditionally been expected to prioritize their roles as caregivers, homemakers, and preservers of family honour. Meanwhile, men have been encouraged to assume positions of authority and responsibility in public life. These gender roles and expectations have perpetuated a patriarchal structure, limiting women's agency and impeding their full participation in various spheres of society.

Can you provide examples of specific rights or opportunities that women were denied or limited in the context of "The Kanun"?

In the context of "The Kanun," women have historically faced limitations and denials of specific rights and opportunities. For instance, women were often denied the right to inherit property, thereby hindering their economic independence and perpetuating dependence on male family members. Additionally, women's participation in public affairs, decision-making processes, and leadership roles was frequently limited, preventing their voices from being heard and their perspectives from being considered.

Moreover, the practice of blood feuds, although not exclusive to "The Kanun," has affected women disproportionately. Women have often been subjected to restrictions on their mobility and freedom, as well as the burden of preserving family honour through their behavior and adherence to societal expectations.

To what extent do you believe these cultural attitudes have persisted in contemporary Albanian society?

While significant progress has been made in recent years, it is important to acknowledge that certain cultural attitudes influenced by "The Kanun" continue to persist in contemporary Albanian society. Despite efforts to promote gender equality and empower women, deep-rooted stereotypes and prejudices can still hinder the full realization of women's rights and their equal participation in all aspects of society.

However, it is crucial to highlight that the recognition of these cultural attitudes and the commitment to change them have gained momentum in contemporary Albania. There is a growing awareness of the need to challenge traditional gender norms and create a more inclusive and equitable society.

In your view, how have these cultural attitudes influenced the participation of women in Albanian politics?

Cultural attitudes influenced by "The Kanun" have historically impacted the participation of women in Albanian politics. Traditional gender roles and expectations have often confined women to the private sphere, limiting their visibility and influence in public life. Women have faced challenges in accessing decision-making positions and encountering biases that undermine their credibility and capabilities.

Nonetheless, I firmly believe that the transformation of our political landscape is underway. Efforts to increase women's representation in politics, such as the implementation of gender quotas and targeted support for women candidates, have gained traction. The active involvement of women in political parties and grassroots movements has been instrumental in challenging these cultural attitudes and amplifying women's voices.

Have there been any notable changes or shifts in the influence of cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" on women's rights and Albanian politics in recent years?

Yes, there have been notable changes and shifts in recent years regarding the influence of cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" on women's rights and Albanian politics. Albania has made significant strides in promoting gender equality and empowering women.

Legal reforms have been enacted to protect women's rights, combat domestic violence, and ensure equal opportunities in various spheres of life. These reforms, coupled with awareness campaigns and educational initiatives, have contributed to a growing recognition of women's rights and their value as active participants in our society.

Moreover, the engagement of women's rights activists, feminist organizations, and civil society movements has been crucial in advocating for change and raising awareness about the negative impact of certain cultural practices. Their efforts have fostered a broader societal dialogue on gender equality and spurred positive transformations in attitudes and perceptions.

How have women's rights activists and feminist movements responded to the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" and their impact on gender equality?

Women's rights activists and feminist movements in Albania have responded proactively to the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" and their impact on gender equality. They have been at the forefront of challenging discriminatory practices and advocating for women's rights.

Through grassroots activism, advocacy campaigns, and awareness-raising initiatives, these activists have worked tirelessly to dismantle harmful norms and raise public consciousness about the importance of gender equality. They have engaged in constructive dialogues with communities, policymakers, and religious leaders to foster a more inclusive understanding of gender roles and promote women's empowerment.

What role do you think policy reforms and legal frameworks have played in addressing the historical marginalization of women's rights in Albania?

Policy reforms and legal frameworks have played a pivotal role in addressing the historical marginalization of women's rights in Albania. They have provided a structured approach to dismantling discriminatory practices and establishing a legal foundation for gender equality. Reforms in areas such as family law, labour rights, and political representation have aimed to rectify historical injustices and ensure women's full participation and empowerment. The implementation of gender quotas, for example, has increased the representation of women in decision-making bodies, promoting a more balanced and inclusive political landscape. Additionally, legal frameworks against domestic violence and gender-based discrimination have enhanced the protection of women's rights, providing avenues for justice and redress. These policy reforms and legal frameworks demonstrate our commitment to promoting gender equality and addressing the historical marginalization of women's rights in Albania.

In your opinion, what are the key challenges that need to be addressed to promote gender equality and overcome the influence of cultural practices on women's rights in contemporary Albanian politics?

Promoting gender equality and overcoming the influence of cultural practices on women's rights in contemporary Albanian politics require a multifaceted approach. While progress has been made, several challenges remain:

- a) Changing societal attitudes and cultural norms: A comprehensive cultural shift is needed to challenge ingrained gender stereotypes and promote equality at all levels. Education and awareness campaigns are essential to challenge harmful norms and foster a more inclusive and egalitarian society.
- b) Enhancing women's political representation: Efforts should continue to be made to increase women's representation in decision-making bodies. This can be achieved through affirmative action measures, mentoring programs, and support networks that enable women to access political leadership positions.

c) Economic empowerment and equal opportunities: Addressing economic disparities and ensuring equal opportunities for women in the workforce are critical. This includes promoting entrepreneurship, providing access to finance and training, and eliminating gender-based pay gaps.

d) Strengthening institutional mechanisms: It is crucial to strengthen institutional mechanisms to protect women's rights, enforce gender equality laws, and provide support services for survivors of gender-based violence.

e) Engaging men as allies: Men must be actively involved in promoting gender equality, challenging harmful cultural practices, and supporting women's empowerment. Engaging men as allies and advocates is instrumental in creating lasting societal change.

By addressing these key challenges, we can foster an inclusive and equitable political environment that recognizes and respects the rights and contributions of all individuals, regardless of gender.

Thank you once again for the opportunity to share my perspectives on this important topic. I hope that our ongoing efforts will continue to shape a more equal and progressive Albania for all its citizens.

Category	Code	Subcode	Interview Examples
Practices	“Cultural Practices” as 1	“Transparency about the tradition” as Subtheme 1.1 “Rooted deeply” as Subtheme 1.2	The cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" (CUL) are deeply rooted in Albania's history and tradition. They developed in response to the challenging conditions faced by the population living in the isolated Albanian mountains (CUL).
	“Women's Rights” as 2	“Limited development of frameworks” as subtheme 2.1	The cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" have historically contributed to the marginalization of women's rights (WR). The context of the time prioritized strength over culture, relegating women to a secondary role (CUL).
Norms	“Cultural Practices” as 3	“Gender influence” as subtheme 3.1	These cultural practices have influenced gender roles and expectations in Albanian society over time, perpetuating traditional norms and reinforcing a patriarchal structure (CUL).
	“Women's Rights” as 4	“Dark History” as a subtheme 4.1	Women were denied or limited in several rights and opportunities in the context of "The Kanun." Examples include restricted inheritance rights, limited decision-making power, and reduced access to education and employment opportunities (WR)

Appendix II

Interview II

The interview is a personal, Email Conducted Interview with a historian and it has been asked to remain anonymous. The interview transcript and answers have been translated from Albanian to English and some answers have had to be redacted from the text therefore it is a summary of the answers. Below is the coded table.

The segments of history in which Albania, especially its inland regions, had the opportunity to develop freely and in peace have been very limited. Throughout the early and late Middle Ages, living in the deep hinterlands of Shkodra and Durres was a continuous existential challenge. In these conditions, the population (mostly indigenous), which lived isolated in the high and almost inaccessible Albanian mountains since at least the late Bronze Age, combining ancient traditions with the need for survival, developed an endemic culture that later gathered and codified itself around the late Middle Ages, in what is known as the Kanun. The Greek word "κανών" chosen to label this set of strict norms came into widespread use after the 4th century and referred to the canonical laws adopted in the Ecumenical Councils. This period coincided with the disintegration of the state during the early Middle Ages, the influx of Slavic peoples, and the merging of several Balkan ethnicities such as Thracians, Dacians, Celts, etc. To escape plundering, murder, or assimilation, the populations residing in the plains sought refuge in the mountains, where they believed they would also be protected by the deities who were believed to dwell there, at least according to the beliefs of that time. For nearly three centuries, from 548 to 820 AD, no form of state control was exerted over any part of the Albanian mountains. Similarly, from around 820 to the beginning of the 13th century - for about four more centuries - no state formation managed to establish a stable presence there to ensure minimal conditions for cultural development. The region lacked cities, schools, and institutions to disseminate knowledge, even at a basic level. The Church also failed to fully penetrate these territories, leaving behind, at best, a moderate paganism and, at worst, ancient superstitious practices, including primitive animism. In these circumstances, where ancient traditions, survival instincts, Roman law, ignorance, and superstition became stratified, the Kanun evolved.

The context of the time favoured strength over culture. Strength was the main element of a society that had to be sustained through heavy physical labour in agriculture, survive through warfare, impose itself through violence and fear, and so on. These factors prioritized men and relegated women to a secondary role. Faced with the waves of history and amidst the total chaos in which the Balkans found themselves at that time, women became fragile creatures constantly endangered by abduction, Slavicization, rape, death (especially during childbirth), and so on.

In fact, we believe that early cultures did not have the marginalization of women as their inherent goal. It emerged later when it was realized that their role, particularly during violent periods of history (such as the Bronze Age, Iron Age, Middle Ages, etc.), was smaller than that of men. It is highly likely that what appears as marginalization today began as a desire to protect and defend women from the aforementioned dangers they seemed weak against. Over time, this evolved into their marginalization and, even worse, their oppression.

We believe that the same thing happened in Albania. Women, who had a much greater role in Illyrian society (see, for example, Melisa, Olympias, Triteuta, Teuta, etc.), were "declassified" into an inferior gender during late antiquity and the early Middle Ages, only to be further marginalized during the late Middle Ages and ultimately suppressed during the five centuries following Ottoman rule. Therefore, from our perspective, the Kanun did not marginalize women; it codified the social reality of the time. Certainly, its codification did not improve their situation in society; on the contrary, it made it more difficult to escape from the state of oppression and isolation. The Kanun had now become an alibi for all those resistant forces that desired to maintain the status quo.

After declaring independence from the Ottoman Empire, the Albanian state faced significant challenges in its establishment. This was due to various reasons, among which the impact of reactionary forces, such as the First World War, was particularly significant. For example, just 18 months after the declaration of independence, a major peasant uprising sought to bring the country back under the rule of the sultan and, above all, demanded the restoration of Sharia law, Islamic religious law, throughout the country. It was only with the installation of King Zog's regime in 1925, 98 years ago, that the work for the restoration of women's dignity in Albanian society would begin.

98 years means 3-4 generations, which from our perspective are completely insufficient in disinfecting the Albanian spirit from the virus of prejudice, which has penetrated so deeply into the nation's cells that, to quote Ismail Kadare (1987), it has caused a "genetic mutation"

in it. Therefore, in our view, it will take much more time and effort for new ideas, concepts, superstitions, or ancient traditions to make way for a new culture in Albania.

The marginalization of women is still a reality today, although it may not be evident in the macro level of laws, strategies, or policies. However, it is deeply felt in the microcosm of the family, public administration, social clubs, businesses, and so on. High femicide rates, sexual harassment in the workplace, selective abortion, workplace discrimination, domestic violence, and even prejudice against clothing are all symptoms of a social pathology that still exists in Albanian society.

Women's emancipation is not merely a legislative fact. While the construction, adoption, and implementation of laws greatly contribute to discouraging discriminatory behavior and encouraging a different mindset, women's emancipation primarily depends on cultural factors and the political context. Women were not marginalized solely by laws, and therefore, their liberation from marginalization will not be achieved solely through legal measures. Opening up to the wider world, existential comparison with emancipated cultures, building self-confidence through experience, creating conditions that favour culture, knowledge, and spirituality over strength, aggression, and violence (characteristics of a deeply patriarchal society) will reposition women in society. It will restore their rightful place as divine mothers, as was once the case .

Category	Code	Subcode	Interview Examples
Culture	“Albanian Politics” as 1	<p>"Fear of judgement" as Subtheme 1.1.</p> <p>"Creativity" as Subtheme 1.2</p> <p>"barrier creation" as Subtheme 1.3</p> <p>"Expressing themselves" as Subtheme 1.4</p>	<p>The cultural attitudes codified in "The Kanun" have influenced the participation of women in Albanian politics by creating barriers and societal expectations that hinder their full engagement.</p>
	“Cultural Practices” as 2	<p>"Transparency about the process" as Subtheme 2.1</p> <p>“Rooted in culture” as Subtheme 2.2</p>	<p>Women's rights activists and feminist movements have responded to the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" by advocating for gender equality, challenging discriminatory norms, and raising awareness about women's rights.</p>
Gender	“Gender Equality” as 1	<p>“Effort put into creating gender transparency” as Subtheme 1.1</p> <p>“Denial and limitations” as Subtheme 2.1</p>	<p>The cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" have historically contributed to the marginalization of women's rights. Women were denied or limited in several rights and opportunities, such as restricted inheritance rights, limited decision-making power, and</p>

Category	Code	Subcode	Interview Examples
			reduced access to education and employment opportunities.
	““Women's Rights” as 2	<p>“Positive feedback and engagement” as Subtheme 3.1</p> <p>“Limited development of frameworks” as subtheme 3.1</p>	<p>The history of Albania, particularly in its inland regions, has had limited opportunities for development and peace. Policy reforms and legal frameworks have played a significant role in addressing the historical marginalization of women's rights in Albania.</p>

Appendix III

This is the script used for the survey, the script is translated from Albanian to English.

The survey included the following key questions:

1. Where do you live?

Albania

Albanian diaspora

Europe

Other

2. Gender:

F

M

Other

3. How old are you?

4. significance in Albania?

A lot

Not at all

Partially

5. To what extent do you believe that the cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" have contributed to the historical marginalization of women's rights?

6. Have you observed the influence of these cultural attitudes on gender roles and expectations in Albanian society?

Yes

No

Maybe

7. Where have you observed this influence? (e.g., education; work; politics)

8. Can you provide specific examples of rights or opportunities that have been denied or restricted for women within the context of "The Kanun"?
9. In your opinion, to what extent do these cultural attitudes continue to exist in Albanian society today?
Yes
No
Partially
10. Have you noticed any change or shift in the influence of cultural practices codified in "The Kanun" on women's rights and Albanian politics in recent years?
Yes
No
Not enough
11. In your opinion, what role have political reforms and legal structures played in addressing the historical marginalization of women's rights in Albania?
12. Based on your opinion, what key challenges need to be addressed to promote gender equality and overcome the influence of cultural practices on women's rights in Albanian politics today?

Appendix IV

Pie charts from the Google forms.

Chart 1. Gender

Chart 2. Geographical distribution

Age Range.

